

Case Study

*Ubuntu Pathways Project
Port Elizabeth, South Africa*

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Introduction

2017: Apple Developer Academy

During the year 2017-18 I took part as student in the advanced training course called Apple Developer Academy in the IT center of the University Federico II in Naples, Italy. The purpose of this course is to train top-class developers through the acquisition of knowledge relating to the fields of coding, design and business.

2018: The PIER Project by Apple Inc.

During the year 2018-19 I was selected among the 500 participants of the 2017-18 course to take part in the PIER project which consists of a research contract for 50 people. The project provides for the in-depth study of the topics studied the previous year and aims to put the participants in front of a real working scenario through the development of an application for an external client.

Ubuntu Pathways Project

During the 2018-19 I had the opportunity to work with Ubuntu Pathways in South Africa.

What is Ubuntu Pathways?

Ubuntu Pathways is an NGO located in the townships of Port Elizabeth in South Africa, the poorest area of the city. Help the community by working with families to develop individualised pathways that can lift them out of poverty.

Ubuntu Pathways is divided into 3 Areas:

- **Clinic**, where they treat mothers with HIV and aim to avoid the transmission of the disease to the foetus and have developed methodologies that allow a success rate of 100%.

- **School**, they have a kindergarten that teaches through learning-by-doing and other cutting-edge techniques, work is underway for the construction of an elementary school.
- **Job Skill Training Program**, an after-school training program in which students take seminars to prepare for the world of work and are put in contact with local companies.

First inspection in Port Elizabeth

Preliminary analysis

We went to Port Elisabeth to get to know the staff, hear about the different problems they face while working and do a domain analysis.

From these meetings we discovered that they use many paper documents and disparate methods to save digital information (mostly spreadsheets).

Each coloured rectangle is a file (or groups of files) that are often not linked and do not communicate with each other. Not all staff can access and view all data, a file cannot be edited simultaneously by multiple people and it often happens that data or cell formulas are lost or corrupted. This leads to frustration, bad communication, wasted time and inefficiency.

For each new data to be entered, the procedure is as follows:

1. Write the news on paper

2. Transcribe the data on an official paper document
3. Record the same on a Google Sheet
4. Update the Excel.

Observation

Analysing the time available and their priorities we decided to focus on the Job Skill Training (JST) Program to create a finished solution and verify that it is functional. A scalable and replicable solution in other areas of the organization, like a brick in a wall that will be built over time.

This is a long-term project, our team can focus on a single area and the next team can continue the project by dealing with other areas.

Research

Our approach was soft-destructive: a solution able to maintain their current workflow, optimising the various phases to the maximum, cutting the use of paper through a digital platform capable of fully organising the management of the JST program. of a long-term project, our team can focus on a single area and the next team can continue the project by dealing with other areas.

The solution is built with FileMaker to have a scalable, secure and cross-platform system. This solution allows the future extension of the project to the Clinic and the educational area.

What is Filemaker?

FileMaker is a platform that provides advanced tools to solve problems and deliver innovation professionally and very quickly, without constraints on a workplace. We can define it as RAD, that is for a low-code rapid development environment (Rapid Ambient Development) and it is also known for the tight integration of the database and the graphical interface.

A Filemaker database can be run through Filemaker itself, or on mobile with the Filemaker Go app, it also allows it to be run in WebDirect or exported both as an executable (Windows, macOS) and as a native app (Android, iOS).

Our solution

The database on FileMaker represents the core and will be placed on a local server so as not to have problems in the event of a network failure, we then designed 3 different solutions for 3 different actors:

1. An iPad app, which is placed on a totem inside the center, it captures people's attention and allows for quick and easy registration to the JST Program.

The registration form app allows you to make a first screening of candidates, analyzing various factors such as age and allows those who register to attach, through the camera, documents and the various certifications required.

2. An iPad app for the Daily Management System, that is the daily assistance that staff members carry out on program users.

Each staff member checks users at different intervals (daily, weekly, monthly, etc.) and of different types such as attendance of courses, family conditions, health, ability to keep a job, etc. We're talking about of a reality totally different from ours where even arriving on time or having an adequate behavior in the workplace are skills obtained through the workshops in the JST program.

3. Admin panel and Management dashboard, (Desktop, Browser, iPad).

The first is a panel for Ubuntu Pathways administrators, they can make changes to data,

download reports on staff work and the status of JST program users, access the graph dashboard, create new login credentials or delete them. The Management dashboard is a reduced view of the panel that contains summaries and graphs on the progress of the JST program, useful for those involved in external relations or for founders.

Development

Through reverse engineering we have analysed all the available documentation, excel and google docs files for the data to be collected and other internal files to reconstruct their work flow, work also useful for asking further questions for a detailed analysis of the requirements.

Development methodology

The team has adopted the Scrum methodology to manage the project ensuring rapid feedback loops with the Ubuntu Pathways referent and frequent tests by the staff.

Second trip to Port Elizabeth

Testing

After six months of development we returned to Port Elizabeth and showed the beta version of the app in the Ubuntu Center. A version created thanks to a direct and constant collaboration with staff members in the design and development phase.

The presentation in Ubuntu Center allowed us to evaluate the use of the app in the daily management of the JST Program. We have gathered a lot of feedback from the people who work there and have found a lot of things to improve.

Using FileMaker allowed us to quickly tweak some elements to test the user experience in real time. In addition, a lexicon check was carried out in the use of the app.

Final result

Registration form

Daily Management System

FROM PRE-JST TO JST CLIENT

A unique work environment where
to keep track of all the services
provided to clients

FROM PRE-JST TO JST CLIENT

A unique work environment where
to keep track of all the services
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Admin e Management Dashboard

CHARTS

A graphics system lets you know what happens in the Ubuntu Center

Charts

Findings

Working with Ubuntu Pathways was a unique experience. An international level experience where I was able to summarise everything I learned in the Engineering Degree Course and at the Apple Developer Academy and apply it in a real environment, but above all I understood the meaning of the word Ubuntu:

Ubuntu is a Nguni Bantu term meaning "humanity".

It is often translated as "I am because we are," or "humanity towards others".

It is often used in a more philosophical sense to mean "the belief in a universal bond of sharing that connects all humanity".